

A Qualitative Evaluation of Parameters Affecting the Performance of Solar Cells at Low Intensity Levels¹

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Abstract

In the energy industry, solar energy and other renewable energy sources are essential because they may decrease the dependency on fossil fuels and other nonrenewable resources such as petroleum and diesel. Photovoltaic cells are clean, sustainable energy sources that are developing quickly. They transform visible light into electrical power. Their low efficiency, however, makes them more expensive than alternative energy sources. This review investigates the factors that determine solar cell efficiency, such as the installation design, solar module, and environmental parameters. By increasing these factors, solar cell efficiency can increase, which will lower output and costs. This study emphasizes the importance of environmental factors, solar module factors, and installation design factors, as well as some unknown and hidden factors, for improving solar cell performance and efficiency.

Keywords

Renewable Energy, Photovoltaic Cells, Efficiency of Solar Cells, Fossil Fuels.

1. Introduction

Solar photovoltaic are a cost-effective and convenient method for obtaining solar energy, "minimizing the consumption of fossil fuels and limiting releases of carbon dioxide" [1]. Both internal and external variables might affect performance with primary metrics such as [2] optimal power, effectiveness, and fill factor [3]. The world's nonrenewable energy supplies are nearly depleted, with only 20% coming from renewable sources such as solar, wind, and hydropower [4]. The largest source of pollution is from nonrenewable sources. The renewable energy source that is expanding most rapidly is solar power [5], which has lower manufacturing costs and greater effectiveness. The effectiveness of solar cells is influenced by different environmental conditions, including temperature, moisture, wind speed, light quality, height, and atmospheric pressure [6]. To improve performance, some hidden aspects such as

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the albedo effect, parasitic resistance, car exhaust smoke effects, and bird waste, should be considered [7]. One can manipulate the parameters to attain optimal energy conversion efficiency. Solar cells are capable of functioning at low intensity under any circumstances.

2. Effect of Parameters

To assess the efficacy of solar cells, it is necessary to investigate certain criteria that have been previously mentioned [8], such as the output power, solar cell efficiency, and fill factor. Furthermore, it is necessary to examine additional aspects to enhance the efficiency of solar cell production. The key factors that directly and indirectly affect the efficiency of solar cells have been identified [9]. Several acknowledged factors include the following:

2.1 Environmental affecting factors

In the process of creating any solar photovoltaic (PV) system, consideration must be given to its influence on the environment, particularly its energy efficiency. The effectiveness of solar panels is contingent upon a wide range of surrounding environmental factors, including

2.1.1 Solar cell Temperature

Temperature is one of the most important factors that determine how well a photovoltaic module performs. It has a negative correlation with both the maximum power and the efficiency of the system. The gap in the band and the reverse saturation current both decrease as the temperature increases [10]. At the same time, this causes an output of low intensity. When the photovoltaic module is heating, its peak level of power (P_{MAX}) and efficacy decrease since they are reliant on the amount of solar irradiation. Additionally, the current increases slightly, while the voltage decreases significantly. Therefore, to improve efficiency, it is recommended that the modules be cooled [3].

In 2019, researchers found that the output of a solar panel is affected by temperature at a variety of temperatures for monocrystalline solar cell modules at different temperatures. During the monitoring process, the voltage and current are observed at three different temperatures: 10, 250, and 500 degrees Celsius. We find that the performance of solar cells has a negative correlation with temperature, which indicates that as temperature increases, the effectiveness of solar cells decreases [6]. The data curve is depicted in Figure 1, and we find that this correlation exists.

Fig. 1: Effect of temperature on the I-V characteristics of solar cell modules [5].

2.1.2 Effect of dust deposition

Research indicates that more dust has a negative impact on the efficiency and fill factor of solar panels, which in turn has an effect on the power and efficiency of these panels. According to the findings of the study, which compared clean and dirty modules, it is necessary to perform periodic cleaning to optimize system performance. This finding highlights the necessity of manufacturing solar panels that are both more efficient and more aesthetically pleasing [3,11].

According to the findings of the study, increased dust levels have a negative impact on the fill factor and efficiency of solar panels, which in turn affects power in addition to efficiency [11]. According to the findings of a study that compared clean and dirty modules and found that periodic cleaning is necessary to improve system efficiency [3], there is a need for solar panels that are both cleaner and more effective.

Fig.2: Optimum power, effectiveness, and fill factor with different dust concentrations on the module [3]

2.1.3 Effect of the Wind speed

The speed of the wind has an effect on the temperature of solar panels, which decreases the temperature and removes dust, hence increasing efficiency. Even at a wind speed that is acceptable, dust that has been deposited can be removed, but wind speeds that are either excessive or low do not increase the power output [3]. The speed of the wind has a beneficial effect on the performance of solar cells because it increases efficiency by lowering the temperature impacts that are exerted on the surface of the cell. One consequence of this is that a decrease in temperature has an effect on the productivity of the solar panel [12]. The efficacy of solar panels is strongly correlated with the speed of the wind, as shown in Figure 3 [5]. Given that the relationship between wind speed and temperature is inverse, it follows that higher wind speeds will result in lower temperatures for the module [13].

Fig. 3: Temperature in relation to wind speed [5].

Fig. 4: Maximum power, efficiency, and fill factor at various wind speeds [3].

2.1.4 Effect of shading on efficiency

Solar radiation in photovoltaic modules can be lowered by shade, which can be either rigid or soft. Several different things, such as leaves, buildings, trees, and bird droppings, can cause this consequence. A mismatch between solar cells, the production of hotspots, and module burns can all be caused by uneven shading. Within the scope of this study, the impacts of shading on the power, efficacy, and fill factor of the module were investigated. This study revealed that both mild and intense shadowing influence performance. To mitigate the impacts of shading, bypass diodes are frequently utilized. It is [3]. Without shadows, solar panels should be installed because even a small amount of shadows can influence the amount of power produced. A series of connections have the potential to disrupt the flow of current,; thus, careful design is essential. It is best to avoid linking panels in series if they receive partial shading [14].

2.1.5 Impact of Humidity

The amount of water droplets that fall on the surface of the module decreases with humidity, which results in a shorter lifespan for the module and causes rust to form on the metal that is used [15]. According to the data presented in Table 2, the relationships between power, voltage, current, and humidity are such that humidity has a negative impact on these variables. Although rainy days cause an increase in relative humidity, moisture leakage causes a decrease in the amount of power that the panels produce [16].

Table 1: Correlations between power, voltage, current and humidity [16].

Time (Hours)	Temperature (°C)	Humidity (%)	Voltage (DC)	Current Amp (DC)	Power (Watt)
8 am	25	25	17.1	2.78	47.5
8:30 am	25	30	16.72	2.63	43.9
9:25 am	25	35	16.53	2.42	40
10:15 am	25	40	16.45	2.3	37.6
10:50 am	25	45	16.41	2.14	35.1
11:30 am	25	50	16.33	2.04	33.3
12:45 pm	25	55	16.32	1.88	30.6

Fig 5: shows voltage versus humidity [16].

Fig. 6: shows the current vs humidity [16].

2.1.6 Rainfall and cloudy atmosphere

Researchers have investigated the effects of cloud cover and humidity [17] on solar panel performance in 2022. They discovered that cloud cover and rain reduce the power and irradiance of solar panels. The average solar output and irradiation decreased by 93.32%, 93.77%, and 71.97%, respectively, on cloudy and wet days. This study emphasizes how crucial it is to consider these variables when producing solar energy [3].

Fig 7: Power and irradiance on a cloudy day [16].

Fig 8: Power and irradiance on a rainy day [16].

Fig 9: Power and irradiance on a sunny day [16].

2.1.7 The Impact of irradiance

The light intensity of a photovoltaic (PV) module depends on how much energy it produces [2]. A review revealed that clear, sunny days yield better performance than do overcast, rainy days. The bulb controls the light intensity and is available in at 100, 800, and 500 W/m². The V-I curve data in Fig. 10 illustrate the light intensity properties of the solar cell [5]. Figure 10 shows the relationship between light intensity and solar cell module performance. There is a direct relationship between the effectiveness and the light intensity, emphasizing the importance of the appropriate light intensity for optimal solar cell performance [18].

Fig 10: The V-I properties of solar cells in relation to light intensity [6, 18]

2.1.8 Color wavelength spectrum

Light wavelengths have a major effect on photovoltaic module production [3]. In an experiment conducted in 2015, researchers compared five different color filters (red, yellow, green, and blue) with white light to demonstrate the impact of light wavelengths on PV module effectiveness [19,2,20]. The temperature, intensity, and color of the light wavelengths that a crystalline solar cell receives affect its electrical output voltage [19].

Table 2: Different colors of light and their corresponding wavelengths.

Colour	Wavelength (nm)
Red	622 – 780
Orange	597 – 622
Yellow	577 – 597
Green	492 – 577
Indigo	420 – 450
Blue	455 – 492
Violet	390 – 455

Fig 11: The voltages, current, and power variation of the module with different colors of the wavelength of light [22, 19].

Fig 12: Variation in efficiency with different light wavelengths [22, 19].

2.1.9 The impact of the air pressure

The weight of air in the atmosphere of the Earth exerts pressure, which is known as air pressure [23], and increases with altitude, causing a downward force on solar radiation photons. This leads to higher electron extraction and short-circuit current in solar cells, improving their performance with increased light intensity [5]. The correlation between air pressure and a solar cell's output voltage and current is depicted in Figures 13 and 14. The output voltage increases due to increasing pressure [5], whereas the current increases with increasing air pressure. [24].

Fig.13. Air pressure (inHg) versus current (mA)[5].

Fig 14: Voltage (V) vs Air pressure (inHg) [5].

2.1.10 Effect of Tilt angle

This study examined the impact of module fixation and orientation on PV system performance. Tilting is more prominent than orientation, and the optimal orientation is facing south. The results showed that the modules performed better at a 45-degree angle of inclination, resulting in better maximum power, efficiency, and fill factor [3].

2.2. According to the solar module

2.2.1 Material choice (mono, polycrystalline, amorphous)

Solar cells have various designs and are classified into three generations [15]: first, second, and third. Wafer-based silicon cells are used in the first generation, thin-film silicon cells are used in the second generation, and developing technologies such as nanocrystals, polymers, dye-sensitized silicon cells, and perovskite-based solar cells are used in the latest generation [26]. Because of their consistent structure and purity, monocrystalline solar modules are more powerful than polycrystalline solar modules. The standard qualification for PV module performance is AM1.5 with STC [26].

Table 3: shows an efficiency comparison across several cell generations [26].

Generation	Type of solar cell	Module efficiency (%)	Applications
First Generation	Monocrystalline type,	14-17.5	Used in conventional surroundings
	Polycrystalline type,	12-14	
Second Generation [27]	Thin film solar cells [27]	16-17	Used in BiPV on smaller power systems
	Copper Indium Gallium Selenide (CIGS)	10-12	
	Amorphous silicon [27]	4-8	
Third Generation	Nanocrystal	7-8	Best suited for areas with normal irradiation
	Dye-sensitized	10	
	Polymer	3-10	
	Perovskites	31	
	Cadmium Tellurium (CdTe) type solar cell	9–11	

2.2.2 Effect of Dust-free coating

Regular cleaning is crucial for solar panels and mirrors due to the significant issue of dust accumulation, which can reduce photovoltaic panel output by up to 30% in a month.

3. According to Solar Installation Design The Key Factors

3.1 Effect of Maximum Power Point Tracking [MPPT]

The attribute of inverters that permits them to sustain the maximum power point (MPP) is also referred to as maximum power point tracking (MPPT) [28]. Owing to its ability to optimize performance and adjust to environmental factors, this function is essential to an inverter's ability to meet grid criteria and regulatory standards at all times of operation. The voltage current that produces the maximum power value on the IV characteristic curve is where the MPP is located. Figure 16 shows the MPP for a module in full sun at various temperatures [29].

Fig 16: MPP of the PV module on its IV curve. [30].

3.2 Effect of the Angle of Tilt

The direction and fixability of the solar module affect the effectiveness and reliability of the solar system [31]. The panels are usually inclined with respect to the south. Nonetheless, research indicates that tilting is more prevalent than inclination. The modules should be oriented with their faces toward the south for the best results. IV and PV curves were drawn in studies conducted in real time [3].

To investigate how a module performs at various tilt angles, the study looks at how the angle of tilt impacts the panel output of power [32]. The maximum benefits are obtained at an inclination of 45 degrees. Increased efficiency, fill factor, and maximum power output. The IV and PV curves at different tilt degrees are displayed in Figures 17 and 18 [3].

Fig.17: IV curve for varied inclination angles [3].

Fig.18: PV curves at various angles [3].

3.3 Effect of Cable Thickness

The sizes of the cables that connect the solar module to measurement devices and the load have a major impact on a solar system's efficiency [33]. Variations in cable size and length can cause resistive losses [3] and increase voltage drops, resulting in lower system output. Additionally, increasing the cable thickness can decrease the voltage drop, thereby increasing the efficiency [15].

The study revealed that the voltage decreases with cable thickness, with 1.5 mm² cables exhibiting a 0.24% decrease and 6 mm² cables exhibiting a 0.06% decrease. The efficiency and fill factor are greater for 6 mm² cables [3].

Table 4: VOLTAGE DROP FOR VARIOUS CABLE SIZES [3]

Sl no	Cable size(mm ²)	Resistance per mtr of length(ohm)	Resistance of 2 mtr wire (ohm)	Voltage drop (volt)
1	1.5	0.012	0.024	0.048
2	3	0.006	0.012	0.025
3	6	0.003	0.006	0.012

4. According to Solar Installation Design the Key Factors

4.1 Orientation

The orientation of a solar panel is crucial for maximizing its power output. Some panels track the sun, while others are fixed in their angle. For optimal efficiency, solar panels should be south-facing, as they face the sun all day, maximizing sunlight collection and energy conversion. Panels facing east or west produce approximately 20% less energy. For homes north of the equator, true south is the proper orientation, while for south-facing homes, the opposite is true north.

4.2 Area of exposure (vertical, horizontal)

A solar panel with numerous cells produces more current than one with a constant voltage output. A larger solar panel area results in a greater amount of solar energy being gathered and transformed into electricity. More sunlight can be absorbed and electricity can be generated because an average solar panel array generates 9–11 kwh per square foot.

4.3. Solar reflector

The reflector enhances solar panels' exposure to solar radiation, thereby increasing their electricity production, which significantly impacts the parameters and I-V characteristic curve of the solar panel. [34].

5. Other Hidden Factors

To characterize and improve the efficiency of solar cells, other parameters need to be studied are:

5.1 The Albedo Effect

Solar cells in solar panels are responsible for the generation of alternating currents by absorbing incoming energy. The radiation that is reflected is lost, which increases the efficiency of solar power. The albedo effect is a method for measuring the amount of light that can be reflected and impacted by solar panels, particularly in coastal areas. Sixteen percent of the energy that is received is converted

into direct current, while the remaining energy is dissipated as heat. The albedo, which is a ratio or fraction that does not have any dimensions, can range from zero to one [35].

5.2 Effect of Parasitic Resistances

The maximum power rectangle (VOC. Both the ISC) and efficiency are impacted by parasitic resistance, which is a substantial source of loss in practical solar cells. Series resistance (R_s) and shunt resistance (R_{sh}) are the sources of this resistance. Both of these resistances are more severe when the photocurrent is large and when there is current leakage around the edges and contacts of the device [29]. Furthermore, the influence of parasitic resistance is especially substantial when coupled with weak rectifying qualities; hence, efficiency is negatively impacted. Nevertheless, recent advancements in cell production and material chemistry management have resulted in significant improvements in the resistivity and efficiency of cells [36, 37, 38].

Fig 19: A useful circuit for an equivalent solar cell [5].

5.3 Effect of Degradation of PV Module

PV solar systems typically guarantee a 25-year performance life for solar modules, with the first few years being the most challenging. The rated power production deteriorates at a rate of 0.5% per year, affecting mechanical, chemical, electrical, or thermal processes. Most performance losses [2] and module failures are caused by prolonged external exposure, yet early deterioration can also be caused by inadequate design, inferior materials, or manufacturing problems [39].

5.4 Effect of Mounting

Most PV power plants are connected in series, and solar panels are normally attached to the ground or roof and installed on steel rails. Panels are usually mounted on rooftops in open locations for residential and small-scale use.

5.5 PID's (potentially induced degradation) effects

In solar systems, an irregular current phenomenon called potential-induced degradation (PID) results in a 30% or greater output loss [40]. This can result in increased recombination and cell damage and is mostly felt in ungrounded inverters. PID arises a few years after the system's implementation [2]. Based on the test findings, there is less of an impact on shunting in the 50 nm-TiO₂ and 100 nm-TiO₂ modules than in the conventional module.

5.6 Car Exhaust Smoke Effect

Due to the extensive installation of PV modules in places such as vehicle stations that produce dangerous smoke, solar energy is expected to displace fossil fuels as a source of electrical energy.

Smoke has varying effects on panel surfaces based on its concentration; it reduces efficiency, voltage, and current [41].

5.7 Bird dropping

Bird droppings can severely damage solar modules, preventing them from generating electricity. Regular cleaning is crucial for maintaining the system's value and ensuring optimal yield. Bird droppings are stubborn and aggressive, causing increased cleaning efforts and potentially etching the solar system. Overlong exposure can lead to significant yield losses for photovoltaic operators. To avoid this, it is recommended that sun brush systems and accessories be used to clean the solar system regularly. This will guard against harm and guarantee peak efficiency [42].

5.8 Reflection

Reducing light reflection from the outside of the solar cell can improve its efficiency since, in silicon solar cells without an antireflection coating; this light reflection makes up approximately 30% of the incident light. Antireflection coating and a rough surface help to achieve this reduction [14].

5.9 Inverter Efficiency

Solar panel inverters are crucial for AC loads, with efficiencies ranging from 80% to 90%. Su Kam's 1000 VA inverter is 85% efficient, while its 2KW–5KW products are more than 87% efficient. UTL's UTL Solar Hoodi Back Up prototypes have 80% efficiency, making them suitable for various applications.

6. Impact of The Low Intensity of Solar Cells

The electricity production of solar cells typically increases in direct proportion to the level of sunlight they receive, meaning that higher sunlight intensity leads to greater energy output. To achieve good solar cell efficiency at a low intensity, the following impacts, must be considered:

6.1 Technological Impact

Energy Conversion and Output

The percentage of the energy that is in the sun that a solar cell can convert into electricity that can be used is the definition of the efficiency of a solar cell. Most solar cells that are available for commercial use have efficiencies ranging between 15% and 22%, which indicates that a significant amount of the solar energy that is received is not captured. Solar energy is not a viable option in densely populated metropolitan contexts because of its poor conversion rate, which requires greater surface areas to create meaningful amounts of power. This makes solar energy less practicable in these environments, where space is at a premium.

Material Utilization

The low efficiency due to the low intensity of solar cells leads to a greater amount of material consumption for each unit of energy that is produced. To attain the desired level of energy output, additional materials must be utilized. These materials include silicon, thin films, and a variety of semiconductors. As a result of this increased demand for raw materials, production costs may increase,

and the environmental footprint associated with mining, processing, and manufacturing these commodities may increase significantly.

6.2 Economic Impact

Cost of Installation

If the intensity level of the solar cell is low, solar cells will have a low efficiency, which contributes to the greater expenses incurred for each watt of electricity generated. Larger arrays of solar panels are required to compensate for reduced efficiency, which results in an increase in the initial capital investment for both residential and commercial systems. It is possible that potential users will be dissuaded from investing in solar technology due to this financial barrier, which will accelerate the transition to renewable energy sources.

Return on Investment

A longer payback period for solar investments is a direct consequence of low efficiency. Compared to alternative methods of energy production, such as fossil fuels or renewable options with better efficiency, such as wind or hydroelectric power, solar energy may be less appealing due to the longer amount of time that is required to recoup the original installation costs through energy savings.

6.3 Environmental Impact

Land Use and Habitat Disruption

When it comes to generating high power outputs, the requirement for extensive solar panel installations might result in a huge amount of land being used. This is a particularly difficult challenge in areas where there is a scarcity of land available or where the preservation of land is a top concern. There is a possibility that large-scale solar farms will have a negative impact on biodiversity since they have the capacity to alter local ecosystems and habitats.

Resource Depletion and Pollution

In regard to generating high power outputs, the requirement for extensive solar panel installations might result in a large amount of land being used. This is a particularly difficult challenge in areas where there is a scarcity of available land or where the preservation of land is a top concern. It is possible that large-scale solar farms will have a negative impact on biodiversity since they have the capacity to alter local ecosystems and habitats.

6.4 Social Impact

Accessibility and Equity

Accessibility can be restricted, particularly for households and communities with low incomes, due to the higher costs and lower returns associated with solar cells with low efficiency. Affluent individuals or areas may be able to afford the transition to renewable energy, while disadvantaged communities continue to rely on traditional energy sources that produce pollution. This economic barrier has the potential to worsen energy disparity.

Public Perception and Adoption Rates

The public's view of solar technology can be influenced by its perceived inefficiency and high costs, which might result in slower adoption rates. It is possible for widespread acceptance and integration of solar systems into mainstream energy infrastructures to be thwarted by the dissemination of false information or the occurrence of negative experiences related to the cost-effectiveness of solar energy.

7. Conclusion

In this review, the most important elements that influence the power, fill factor, and efficiency of solar photovoltaic (PV) systems are investigated. Temperature and irradiance are the most important parameters; other factors that influence these factors include tilt angle, dust, shade, wind speed, cable thickness, color spectrum, humidity, and mounting. Module tracking, on the other hand, can be utilized to achieve maximum power, which enables the system to operate at its peak regardless of the weather outside and makes it easier to make effective use of photovoltaic (PV) systems. We also need to improve and control other hidden factors, such as the albedo effect, the effect of parasitic resistivity, the degradation of PV modules, the car exhaust smoke effect, bird dropping, PIDs (potentially induced degradation), and reflection, among others, as discussed above, to achieve better efficiency and even allow solar cells to function at low intensity levels.

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